

USING FOREIGN EXPERIENCES IN TEACHING GEOGRAPHY SUBJECT WITH DIGITAL TECHNOLOGIES AND APPLYING THEM

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Abstract. *In today's teaching of subjects, active use of information and learning environments, educational platforms, and educational websites contributes to improving the effectiveness of teaching, shaping and developing students' competencies. In addition to geography, utilizing information learning environments is crucial in the educational and upbringing process. Therefore, to enhance the efficiency of teaching geography in our country, it is essential to use digital technologies, especially in shaping and developing students' geographical competencies in educational environments. For this purpose, studying foreign experiences is necessary. Accordingly, within the framework of research, the state of teaching geography in foreign general education schools, vocational colleges, and higher education institutions was analyzed.*

Keywords: *critical thinking, PISA testing system, Interactive educational tools, logical thinking, CNED, distance education.*

Introduction. In enhancing the effectiveness of teaching geography in foreign countries' schools, active use of digital technologies is being employed to develop students' cognitive independence, decision-making abilities, and practical skills. However, it is evident from research that our country has not paid sufficient attention to the utilization of digital technologies in teaching geography in general education schools. This lack of emphasis on using digital technologies has led to a neglect of improving students' knowledge, skills, competencies, and abilities in this subject.

Consequently, it is crucial to recognize the necessity of adopting new approaches in utilizing digital technologies to enhance the teaching of geography in our country's general education schools. To address this, it is essential to gather and analyze the opinions and experiences of foreign experts who have effectively utilized digital technologies in teaching geography.

Materials and research methods.

American educational institutions in the United States prioritize teaching geography differently. "In American middle schools, geography is taught separately, with integration into social studies". In the United States, there are well-developed distance learning systems and educational environments designed for teaching geography. For example, the "Washington Academy American Online High School Diploma" is a modern distance learning system that can be cited as an example. (In our country's general education schools, information learning environments have been created for teaching geography outside of class hours). This teaching system enhances students' logical thinking and provides opportunities for independent learning.

Furthermore, "K12 International Academy" portal is actively used for teaching geography in a modern way, offering video lessons, hypermedia information, self-assessment, and various tests (Open, Closed, and PISA tests) as well as a bank of practical tasks. These digital resources contribute to the success of teaching geography in American schools and enable students to receive independent education.

"In Canadian schools, teaching geography in other subjects is given special attention. In Canada, there are ample opportunities for online learning, with many virtual schools in operation (virtual schools are not currently established in our country). Additionally, Canada has the "Contact North" distance learning organization, which allows students, especially in geography, to receive continuous education". Moreover, in this country, natural science subjects are actively taught in open and closed learning environments. These environments include geography-related video lessons, virtual learning technologies, and online tests.

Research and results.

In French schools, personalized teaching technologies are used to organize students' learning activities both in and outside the classroom based on various teaching technologies. "Through these technologies, geography lessons are designed to give teachers more flexibility in imparting the content, methods, and resources required to achieve high results. Additionally, special excursions are organized, including those conducted in national or regional nature reserves and uncharted territories". Various natural and regional complexes are visited in one day to introduce students to different conditions (In our country's general education schools, it is possible to organize excursions outside of class hours). Furthermore, in France, computer technologies, specifically interactive learning tools, are effectively used to personalize geography-related information. Interactive learning tools help students visualize geographic phenomena and events in a visual format and expand their imagination. Additionally, in this country, interactive tests and practical tasks have been developed on the web to effectively organize out-of-class learning activities and promote logical thinking. This allows students to benefit from self-assessment opportunities.

Moreover, in France, the NCDL (National Center for Distance Learning) is actively involved in teaching subjects, especially geography. This teaching system enables students to study geography in a distance learning environment, organize independent evaluations, and complete assignments (In our country, the Republican Educational Center's information learning environment <https://dr.rtm.uz/> is available for students to independently study geography).

In German schools, the topics covered in the geography curriculum are mostly related to patriotism. German schools organize a variety of activities for teaching geography both within and outside the classroom over the course of 7-8 days. These activities include excursions to locations such as national parks and remote areas within the country (In our country's general education schools, organizing activities outside of class hours is often considered). In addition to excursions, there are other types of outdoor activities, such as teamwork games (project work), ecological campaigns (improving the environment), and field geographical investigations. Furthermore, in Germany, the PISA tests related to geography are used to evaluate and assess students' logical thinking abilities. Students have the flexibility to use these tests at their preferred time and location (In our country, mechanisms for conducting PISA tests in schools are being developed).

In the United Kingdom, the educational system pays special attention to geography, considering it an important and compulsory subject. Geography is taught in grades 1-9 in British

schools. (In our country, geography is taught in grades 5-10). Students are encouraged to independently gather and later use geographic knowledge. In addition, there are specialized field research centers for geography in the United Kingdom. These centers have all the necessary equipment and facilities, which are made available to schools for conducting complete scientific investigations in the field. (In our country, it is possible for students to independently organize field research).

Personalized research findings are used in final examinations based on the results of the PISA tests (In our country, exams are based on the information taught in the classroom). Moreover, in the United Kingdom, special teaching systems and platforms have been created to facilitate independent learning of geography. "Students have the opportunity to use them wherever and whenever they want. These educational resources help students effectively. In addition, there are accredited online schools in the United Kingdom that offer comprehensive education. For example, schools like InterHigh, Tute, British School, First College, and Net-School are available" The teaching of geography in foreign countries like Italy, the Czech Republic, Hungary, Poland, Russia, Turkey, and Uzbekistan, as mentioned earlier, also involves the use of active learning methods, both in traditional classroom settings and through virtual educational technologies.

Based on the observations of the development of geography education in foreign countries, it can be noted that there is no single prescribed teaching system. In general, in foreign countries, the teaching of geography is oriented towards:

1. Developing cognitive activities in the context of psychological guidance, including problem-based learning, understanding students' age and individual characteristics, using games, implementing scientific projects, and more.
2. Teaching geographic concepts and skills essential to understanding dynamic changes in the environment and society, as well as fostering analysis and synthesis.
3. Providing knowledge, skills, and competencies related to the geographical aspects of traveling in the modern world and understanding the nature and dynamics of the main regions where travel can occur.
4. Developing the ability to make full use of the resources of the natural environment in order to shape the national and global cultural heritage.
5. Enhancing knowledge about natural, historical, and cultural conditions in the context of changing economic, ecological, and political systems, as well as the peculiarities of international geographic labour distribution.

Conclusion. Overall, it can be seen that in developed countries, special attention is paid to practical activities in teaching geography, which is not yet the case in our country's general education schools. To address this gap, the implementation of such opportunities in a virtual format is considered appropriate. Additionally, aligning these opportunities with the goals of the PISA tests for assessing students' logical thinking in geography is relevant. Furthermore, in teaching geography, it is essential to leverage both games and digital technologies. In this context, integrating digital technologies and game-based methods into lessons can lead to effective results.

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